

Ishtar's Temple/Temple D on the Acropolis (Tell Mardikh/ancient Ebla)

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Entry tags: Temple, Middle Bronze Age, northern Levant, Religious Group, Middle Bronze I-II (Old Syrian Period), north-western inner Syria, Near East, Ancient Syrian Religion, Religious Place, Archaeological monument, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult

Temple D on the Acropolis is an imposing temple building erected in the ancient city of Ebla (present-day Tell Mardikh), the most important cult building within the Citadel of the Old Syrian town. It dates back to c. 2000-1600 BCE (in the traditional middle chronology), the Middle Bronze I-II of north-western inland Syria chronology. It was the dynastic sanctuary dedicated to the great Ishtar, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla during the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides; a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the open air in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially recovered and reconstructed from two large fragments in 2006. As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (perhaps one of the two found inside the temple). The temple was probably erected during the first decades of the second millennium BCE. It stood along the western edge of the fortified Acropolis, over a large mudbrick terrace which enclosed the levelled ruins of the previous Early Bronze IVA Kura's Temple in the SA.ZA. The building (some 30 m long and 11.50 m wide), facing south, had a longitudinal, axial, tripartite structure (with vestibule, antecella and cella), with an entrance delimited by projecting antae: a layout that from now on will characterize the palatine and dynastic temples in the Levant, erected in the citadels close to royal palaces. It featured a quite short vestibule preceded by two steps (L.213), an equally short antecella (L.211), and a marked longroom cella (L.202), 12.40 m long and 7.20 m wide; such a marked longitudinal development of the cella is canonical in the Middle Bronze Age temples in Ebla and inland Syria (a few exceptions can be mentioned, as the Alalakh VII Temple and the MBA Hadad's Temple in Aleppo). The cella had a low bench against the back wall, onto which opened a quite deep, almost square niche for the cult image. Several remains of important basalt and limestone cult fittings (e.g., two basins and an offering table) were found inside the cella. Moreover, the entrance to the cella probably featured basalt jambs decorated with two big carved images of lying lions. In front of the temple there was a large open space, gradually sloping towards the south, which housed monumental cult fittings, including a big limestone round basin found in situ. Ishtar's Temple on the Citadel was destroyed around 1600 BCE, when the whole Old Syrian city was devastated by a Hittite-Hurrian coalition headed by Mursili I of Hatti and Pizikarra of Nineveh (Matthiae 1981, 114-116, 130-132; 2021, pp. 198-203, 322-325).

Date Range: 2000 BCE - 1600 BCE

Region: Ebla / Tell Mardikh

Region tags: Syria, North-western inner Syria

The archaeological site of Tell Mardikh, ancient Ebla, is located in upper inner Syria, 55 km south of Aleppo. The site has an extension of 56 hectares. It has been

continuously excavated by an archaeological expedition of the Sapienza University of Rome between 1964 and 2010, for 47 uninterrupted campaigns, which brought to light the large fortified urban settlements of the Early Bronze and Middle Bronze Ages (mature/late Early Syrian Period and Old Syrian Period).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Acropolis of the Old Syrian town

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: It was around 30 m long on the south-north axis and 11.50 m wide on the east-west one.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Mudbrick terrace

Notes: Built by levelling and enclosing the ruins of the previous Early Bronze IV A Kura's Temple

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Political

Notes: The temple was the the dynastic sanctuary of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla, dedicated to the great Ishtar, patron goddess of the city.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Notes: With the exception of some internal refurbishments (e.g., the refurbishment of the inner floor).

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: Ishtar's Temple on the Citadel was destroyed at the same time as the whole Old Syrian city, at the end of Middle Bronze II, around 1600 BCE (in the traditional middle chronology).

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Crisis and Collapse: Similarity and Diversity in the Three Destructions of Ebla from EB IVA to MB II". *Scienze Dell'antichità* 15 (2009): 43-83.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of war

Notes: The conquest and destruction of the of the Old Syrian city by a Hittite-Ilurrian coalition headed by Mursili I of Hatti and Pizikarra of Nineveh, around 1600 BCE.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

Notes: After the destruction of the Old Syrian city around 1600 BCE, the temple was reduced and adapted to more modest functions of worship. The cult place might have become an open-air sanctuary.

↳ In antiquity
– Once

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Ishtar Eblaitu, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone lustral double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides (Matthiae 1981, 135–136); a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 (Matthiae 2013 [1986]) and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially reconstructed from five fragments (Matthiae 2021). As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt votive statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple; Matthiae 2021, fig. 9.1), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (probably one of the two found inside the temple).

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "An Archaic Old Syrian Stele from Ebla and the Figurative Culture of Syria Around 1800 BC". In *Studies on the Archaeology of Ebla 1980-2010*, 517–55. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2013. https://www.harrassowitz-verlag.de/title_4457.html.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "The Obelisk of Ishtar from Ebla. Kingship and the Great Goddess in the Old Syrian Artistic Culture". *Studia Eblaitica* 7, no. 1 (2021): 123–58. <https://doi.org/10.13173/steb/2021/1/123>.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "About the Identity of the Titular Deities of the Old Syrian Temples of Ebla". In *Studies on the Archaeology of Ebla 1980-2010*, 301–22. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2013. https://www.harrassowitz-verlag.de/title_4457.html.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. *Ebla. An Empire Rediscovered*. Garden City, New York : Doubleday &

Company, Inc., 1981.

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Matthiae, P. 2021. Ebla : Archaeology and History . London / New York : Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- Source 2: Matthiae, P. 1981. Ebla. An Empire Rediscovered. Garden City, New York : Doubleday & Company, Inc.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing

Notes: The temple was erected over a kind of mudbrick terrace which enclosed the levelled the ruins of the previous Early Bronze IV A Kura's Temple

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of excavation:
 - Scientific

- ↳ Years of excavation:
 - Year range: 1965-1966

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, Ebla (MAIS)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: However, the temple was isolated and independent from the adjacent buildings.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The temple was located within the Citadel of the Old Syrian town along the western edge of the fortified hill, near the region of the Royal Palace E, which was the seat of political power in the first half of the second millennium BCE.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The Old Syrian kings of Ebla

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The temple was built within the fortified Citadel of the Old Syrian town, near the region of the Royal Palace E.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of devotion with expectation of approval and protection over the ruling dynasty.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

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Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1965-1966

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Acropolis of the Old Syrian town

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

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– Yes

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– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

Notes: The temple was erected over a kind of mudbrick terrace which enclosed the levelled the ruins of the previous Early Bronze IV A Kura's Temple

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The temple was built within the fortified Citadel of the Old Syrian town, near the region of the Royal Palace E.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: It was around 30 m long on the south-north axis and 11.50 m wide on the east-west one.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Mudbrick terrace

Notes: Built by levelling and enclosing the ruins of the previous Early Bronze IV A Kura's Temple

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Political

Notes: The temple was the the dynastic sanctuary of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla, dedicated to the great Ishtar, patron goddess of the city.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

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Notes: With the exception of some internal refurbishments (e.g., the refurbishment of the inner floor).

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↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

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↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: After the destruction of the Old Syrian city around 1600 BCE, the temple was reduced and adapted to more modest functions of worship. The cult place might have become an open-air sanctuary.

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Ishtar Eblaitu, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone lustral double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides (Matthiae 1981, 135-136); a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 (Matthiae 2013 [1986]) and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially reconstructed from five fragments (Matthiae 2021). As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt votive statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple; Matthiae 2021, fig. 9.1), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (probably one of the two found inside the temple).

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↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The Old Syrian kings of Ebla

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of devotion with expectation of approval and protection over the ruling dynasty.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: E.g., the entrance to the cella featured basalt jambs decorated with two big carved images of lying lions.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Double rectangular cult basins in basalt or limestone decorated with mythical and ritual depictions in relief, a particular kind of stone furniture that characterizes the cult buildings in Old Syrian Ebla.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Old Syrian Statuary and Carved Basins from Ebla. New Documents and Interpretations". In *Les Espaces Mesopotamiens. Dimensions De L'experience Humaine Au Proche-orient Ancien. Volume D'hommage Offert a Jean-claude Margueron (subartu XVII)*, 423–38. Turnhout: Brepols, 2006. <https://www.brepols.net/products/IS-9782503520230-1>.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For example, on one side of the basin of Temple D, a heroic-mythical being with a lion's head is depicted, while he is grasping two lions by the hind legs; while on the Ishtar's Stele bullmen, a man-headed bull and a tetramorphic sphinx with a human face, both with the usual divine tiara, are depicted.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Votive statues, probably royal, should have been dedicated in the temple, as it happened in the Ishtar's Temple (Temple P2) in the Lower Town. In fact, besides the Ibbit-Lim's statue found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple, fragments of votive statues of kings and queens were found at the foot of the Acropolis, below the Ishtar's Temple, where they were probably thrown after being broken to pieces during the final conquest of the city.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "High Old Syrian Royal Statuary from Ebla". In *Von Uruk Nach Tuttul. Eine Festschrift Für Eva Strommenger. Studien Und Aufsätze Von Kollegen Und Fremden* (münchener Vorderasiatische Studien 12), 111-28. München: Profil Verlag, 1992.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Old Syrian Statuary and Carved Basins from Ebla. New Documents and Interpretations". In *Les Espaces Mesopotamiens. Dimensions De L'expérience Humaine Au Proche-orient Ancien. Volume D'hommage Offert a Jean-claude Margueron (subartu XVII)*, 423–38. Turnhout: Brepols, 2006.
<https://www.brepols.net/products/IS-9782503520230-1>.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: E.g., the entrance to the cella featured basalt jambs decorated with two big carved images of lying lions.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Animals: lying lions, symbolic animal of the goddess Ishtar

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Field doesn't know

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

- Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No

- ↳ Humans
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes

Notes: Divine subjects and mythical depictions

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Ritual depictions

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 345

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, the thickness of the perimeter walls indicates a considerable height of the building.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Used to make the foundations

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

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Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

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↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Used to make the foundations

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: E.g., the entrance to the cella featured basalt jambs decorated with two big carved images of lying lions.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Double rectangular cult basins in basalt or limestone decorated with mythical and ritual depictions in relief, a particular kind of stone furniture that characterizes the cult buildings in Old Syrian Ebla.

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↳ Are there humans depicted:

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↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For example, on one side of the basin of Temple D, a heroic-mythical being with a lion's head is depicted, while he is grasping two lions by the hind legs; while on the Ishtar's Stele bullmen, a man-headed bull and a tetramorphic sphinx with a human face, both with the usual divine tiara, are depicted.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Votive statues, probably royal, should have been dedicated in the temple, as it happened in the Ishtar's Temple (Temple P2) in the Lower Town. In fact, besides the Ibbit-Lim's statue found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple, fragments of votive statues of kings and queens were found at the foot of the Acropolis, below the Ishtar's Temple, where they were probably thrown after being broken to pieces during the final conquest of the city.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "High Old Syrian Royal Statuary from Ebla". In *Von Uruk Nach Tuttul. Eine Festschrift Für Eva Strommenger. Studien Und Aufsätze Von Kollegen Und Fremden (münchener Vorderasiatische Studien 12)*, 111–28. München: Profil Verlag, 1992.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Old Syrian Statuary and Carved Basins from Ebla. New Documents and Interpretations". In *Les Espaces Mesopotamiens. Dimensions De L'expérience Humaine Au Proche-orient Ancien. Volume D'hommage Offert a Jean-claude Margueron (subartu XVII)*, 423–38. Turnhout: Brepols, 2006.
<https://www.brepols.net/products/IS-9782503520230-1>.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: E.g., the entrance to the cella featured basalt jambs decorated with two big carved images of lying lions.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Animals: lying lions, symbolic animal of the goddess Ishtar

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Divine subjects and mythical depictions

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Ritual depictions

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

|

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The great goddess Ishtar, city goddess and dynastic goddess, patron and protecting the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties.

- ↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they sky deity:
 - Yes

Notes: The Ishtar's Stele and the Ishtar's Obelisk, which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, depict a great goddess's figure in a winged chapel, hinting at her nature as deity of heaven where she dwells.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

- Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

- Yes

Notes: The theme of the sacred banquet, with the king and a priestess as protagonists, is represented on the main face of the carved limestone basin discovered in place in the southwest corner of the cella.

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Priests
 - No
 - ↳ Local elites
 - Yes

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community
– Field doesn't know

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla, the dignitaries of the kingdom and the priesthood, together with those who performed the rituals (musicians, servants. etc.).

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:
– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The great goddess Ishtar, city goddess and dynastic goddess, patron and protecting the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Ishtar's Stele and the Ishtar's Obelisk, which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, depict a great goddess's figure in a winged chapel, hinting at her nature as deity of heaven where she dwells.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Field doesn't know

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla, the dignitaries of the kingdom and the priesthood, together with those who performed the rituals (musicians, servants. etc.).

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: The theme of the sacred banquet, with the king and a priestess as protagonists, is represented on the main face of the carved limestone basin discovered in place in the southwest corner of the cella.

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Field doesn't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time
– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Ishtar's Temple/Temple D on the Acropolis (Tell Mardikh/ancient Ebla), Matthiae, Paolo. Ebla. An Empire Rediscovered. Garden City, New York : Doubleday & Company, Inc., 1981.

Reference: Ishtar's Temple/Temple D on the Acropolis (Tell Mardikh/ancient Ebla), Matthiae, Paolo. Ebla: Archaeology and History. London; New York: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, 2021.
<https://www.routledge.com/Ebla-Archaeology-and-History/Matthiae/p/book/9780367494407>.

Reference: Ishtar's Temple/Temple D on the Acropolis (Tell Mardikh/ancient Ebla), Matthiae, Paolo. "Archeologia Del Culto a Ebla: Residenze Degli Dèi E Ideologia Della Regalità". In *L'archeologia Del Sacro E L'archeologia Del Culto: Sabratha, Ebla, Ardea, Lanuvio* (roma, 8-11 Ottobre 2013). Ebla E La Siria Dall'età Del Bronzo All'età Del Ferro, 17-63. Rome: Bardi Edizioni, 2016.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Matthiae, Paolo. "Crisis and Collapse: Similarity and Diversity in the Three Destructions of Ebla from EB IVA to MB II". *Scienze Dell'antichità* 15 (2009): 43-83.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Ishtar Eblaitu, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone lustral double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides (Matthiae 1981, 135-136); a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 (Matthiae 2013 [1986]) and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially reconstructed from five fragments (Matthiae 2021). As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt votive statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple; Matthiae 2021, fig. 9.1), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (probably one of the two found inside the temple)., Matthiae, Paolo. "An Archaic Old Syrian Stele from Ebla and the Figurative Culture of Syria Around 1800 BC". In *Studies on the*

Archaeology of Ebla 1980-2010, 517-55. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2013. https://www.harrassowitz-verlag.de/title_4457.ahtml.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Ishtar Eblaitu, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone lustral double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides (Matthiae 1981, 135-136); a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 (Matthiae 2013 [1986]) and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially reconstructed from five fragments (Matthiae 2021). As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt votive statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple; Matthiae 2021, fig. 9.1), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (probably one of the two found inside the temple), Matthiae, Paolo. "The Obelisk of Ishtar from Ebla. Kingship and the Great Goddess in the Old Syrian Artistic Culture". *Studia Eblaitica* 7, no. 1 (2021): 123-58. <https://doi.org/10.13173/stebbla/2021/1/123>.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Ishtar Eblaitu, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone lustral double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides (Matthiae 1981, 135-136); a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 (Matthiae 2013 [1986]) and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially reconstructed from five fragments (Matthiae 2021). As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt votive statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple; Matthiae 2021, fig. 9.1), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (probably one of the two found inside the temple), Matthiae, Paolo. "About the Identity of the Titular Deities of the Old Syrian Temples of Ebla". In *Studies on the Archaeology of Ebla 1980-2010*, 301-22. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2013. https://www.harrassowitz-verlag.de/title_4457.ahtml.

Reference: Yes, Matthiae, Paolo. "High Old Syrian Royal Statuary from Ebla". In *Von Uruk Nach Tuttul. Eine Festschrift Für Eva Strommenger. Studien Und Aufsätze Von Kollegen Und Fremden (münchener Vorderasiatische Studien 12)*, 111-28. München: Profil Verlag, 1992.

Reference: Yes, Matthiae, Paolo. "Old Syrian Statuary and Carved Basins from Ebla. New Documents and Interpretations". In *Les Espaces Mesopotamiens. Dimensions De L'experience Humaine Au Proche-orient Ancien. Volume D'hommage Offert a Jean-claude Margueron (subartu XVII)*, 423-38. Turnhout: Brepols, 2006. <https://www.brepols.net/products/IS-9782503520230-1>.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Ishtar Eblaitu, the city goddess and the patron goddess of the Old Syrian kings of Ebla in the age of the Amorite Dynasties. This is testified by fragments of monumental furniture that portray the great goddess and her attributes, found inside and outside the temple: a limestone lustral double basin still in place within the temple, with mythical and ritual depictions in relief on three of the sides (Matthiae 1981, 135-136); a second fragmentary basalt basin from inside the temple; and two basalt votive monuments which probably stood in the square in front of the sanctuary, the Ishtar's Stele discovered in 1986 (Matthiae 2013 [1986]) and the Ishtar's Obelisk, partially reconstructed from five fragments (Matthiae 2021). As far as written evidence is concerned, Temple D on the Acropolis is the one mentioned in the inscription carved on Ibbit-Lim's basalt votive statue (found reused at a short distance from the facade of the temple; Matthiae 2021, fig. 9.1), which commemorates the dedication to the goddess Ishtar of a basin (probably one of the two found inside the temple), Matthiae, Paolo. *Ebla. An Empire Rediscovered*. Garden City, New York : Doubleday & Company, Inc., 1981.